

INTEGRATED TEACHING USING VIRTUAL REALITY AND
AUGMENTED REALITY TECHNOLOGIES IN
HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.

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Abstract : In this work It is said that Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) technologies have the ability to make new changes in the modern education system and that these technologies help make the educational process more interactive, interesting and effective. Before analyzing how VR and AR technologies are important in the education system, let's briefly touch on the nature of these technologies.

Key words: Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, technology, practical training, Interactive training, 3D form.

Virtual Reality (VR) technology takes the user into a completely virtual environment. With the help of special VR glasses and equipment, the user can enter the virtual world, perform various tasks there, work in virtual environments created by the teacher or the program.

Augmented Reality (AR) is a technology for superimposing virtual elements such as graphics, sounds, video, and other digital information on top of a real-world environment. AR technology allows the user to add additional information or interactive elements without changing the real world. This technology is usually implemented through smartphones, tablets or special AR glasses.

VR and AR technologies allow students to directly learn course materials in an interactive way. Through VR technologies, students can conduct practical training in various subjects in a virtual environment. For example, in history classes, you can travel through ancient cities using VR, or in biology classes, you can study the internal parts of the human body. AR technologies allow students to interact with various objects and content in a real environment. For example, a world map can be viewed and studied through AR in geography classes[1-2].

Through VR technologies, students are given the opportunity to conduct practical training in a safe environment. This is especially important in fields such as medicine, chemistry and engineering. For example, medical students can learn and practice surgical procedures through VR. This allows them to prepare for complex real-life surgical procedures. In chemistry classes, various chemical reactions can be conducted in a safe environment using VR.

With the help of AR technologies, it becomes easier to visualize the teaching materials. Readers can view the images in the book using AR and see them in 3D. This is especially useful in subjects such as biology, geography and architecture. For example, cell structure or the geological structure of mountains can be studied in detail through AR.

VR and AR technologies allow an individual approach to each student. Readers can study at their own pace and choose content that suits their interests. This is especially important in preschool and primary education, as children at this age have different abilities and interests. VR and AR technologies enable teachers to create lessons that are tailored to the needs of each student.

Research shows that VR and AR technologies increase the effectiveness of learning. Through these technologies, the educational process becomes more interesting and memorable. Students can better understand and remember the material they are learning in a virtual environment or through AR. For example, in math classes, through VR, geometry shapes can be viewed in 3D and analyzed.

VR technologies also offer the possibility of collaboration with many people. Students can work together, solve problems and implement projects in a virtual environment. It helps them to develop cooperation skills and solve real-life problems together. For example, VR allows students to work together on different projects, which helps them understand their roles in a team and develop communication skills.

VR and AR technologies bring innovation to the educational process. With these technologies, teachers can create new teaching styles and apply new approaches to teaching students. With the help of AR technology, it is possible to show the animal world in 3D in biology and explain to the students the anatomical structure of each animal. VR technology allows to realize different experiences from physics in a virtual environment.

VR and AR technologies can help students improve their digital literacy. By

working with these technologies, students develop skills in using modern technologies. This gives them the skills they need to succeed in various fields in the future. With AR and VR, students can learn programming, design, and other digital skills.

In conclusion, it can be said that VR and AR technologies occupy an important place in the field of education. Through these technologies, the educational process can be raised to a more effective, interesting and easy-to-learn level. In the future, VR and AR technologies are expected to develop further, giving rise to new teaching methods that provide more interactive and individualized approaches. With the wider use of these technologies in the education system, the effectiveness of the delivery of modern knowledge and skills can be

increased. The implementation of these technologies requires, first of all, to train teachers and students to use them. At the same time, educational institutions need to create the necessary infrastructure to implement VR and AR technologies. Such steps ensure high-quality and innovative educational process at all levels of education[3-9].

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